

PRE-SERVICE VISUAL ARTS TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THEIR METHODS COURSE IN NATIONAL TEACHER COLLEGES IN UGANDA

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Abstract:

This research aimed to investigate the second year pre-service visual arts teachers' (PVATs) perceptions of the effectiveness of their methods course in equipping them with the knowledge and skills of teaching during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda and how it improved their teaching competence levels. The content for the methods course is aimed at preparing PVATs for school practice. The preparation is done while PVATs are still at college. The study followed a quantitative research design where a self-constructed questionnaire was administered to fifty-two PVATs who had just returned from school practice. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data collected through the questionnaires. The overall findings showed that PVATs needed urgent remedial support in using a variety of teaching and learning resources; lesson planning and implementation; using a variety of teaching methods and using a variety of assessment strategies. It was recommended that NTCs administration revise the methods course content and include technology-based content, conducting methods course content lectures right from the first term of an academic year, refresh tutors' knowledge of the methods course content and ensure regular attendance of both tutors and PVATs.

Keywords: visual arts teachers, methods course, pre-service teachers

1. Introduction

Teacher education programs are intended to equip pre-service visual arts teachers (PVATs) with knowledge and skills for teaching. Basic knowledge for effective teaching is fundamentally acquired by PVATs within the teacher colleges before they are deployed to teach in secondary schools. This kind of knowledge is taught to PVATs through

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methods course. Some of the knowledge for effective teaching PVATs discuss include; pedagogical knowledge, curriculum knowledge, knowledge of learners, context among others (Shulman, 1986/1987). Therefore, possession of such knowledge-base is critical in the teaching and learning process.

1.1 Background to the Study

Teacher preparation in National Teacher Colleges (NTCs) is carried out in two main departments. One is the department of foundation and curriculum. This is where PVATs acquire knowledge of general pedagogy. In this department pre-service teachers are exposed to the philosophy of education, history of education, curriculum studies, teachers' professional ethics, education administration and management and general methods of teaching. The second department is in charge of content (for example; painting, drawing, sculpture, etc.) and it is commonly referred to as the art department. During teacher preparation, PVATs are exposed to a Diploma in Secondary Education (DSE) curriculum which includes disciplines like two dimensional art (2D-art) (graphic design and studio technology, painting and studio technology, drawing and studio technology-still-life, nature study and figure drawing.), three dimensional arts (3D-art) (sculpture and studio technology, and pottery and studio technology and multi-media crafts) and theory which include; principles and methods of teaching art, art history and art appreciation, and marketing (DSE, 2002). From the information above, the methods course is handled in two departments. In the department of foundation and curriculum where it is referred to as general methods of teaching and in the art department the same course now become specific and code-named principles and methods of teaching art. Therefore, this research focuses on the principles and methods of teaching art course or methods course pre-service visual arts teachers are exposed to during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda.

2. The Art Methods Course in NTCs in Uganda

The content for the methods course in NTCs in Uganda includes; the meaning of art, child art and developmental stages in art. It introduces PVATs to secondary school syllabus and teacher resources; such as the scheme of work, and lesson plan. PVATs are expected to deal with evaluation and assessment and methods of teaching art. Through the methods course, pre-service teachers acquire knowledge of teaching and learning. The content for the methods course is aimed at preparing PVATs for school practice but before the actual teaching. According to DSE curriculum, PVATs are first introduced to methods course in their second term of the first year and reappears in the second term the second year which marks the end of their training. In other words, the methods course regardless of how much content, it is taught to the PVATs a few weeks to the school practice in both years. A question raised here is how do tutors go about the methods course content to be able to prepare a competent art teacher who is ready for actual school practice given the short period?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Importance of Methods Course

During methods course, PVATs are introduced to how learners construct knowledge and acquire skills, and how learners develop habits of mind and positive dispositions towards learning (Abisamra, 2010). This is when PVATs acquire knowledge of cognitive, social and developmental theories of learning and how they apply to their learners in the classroom. Besides, methods course also includes; i) classroom management, ii) lesson plan development and implementation, iii) learners evaluation, iv) techniques or methods used in the classroom, v) the nature of the target audience, and vi) strategies for evaluating learners' understanding (Abisamra, 2010). The general belief in NTCs in Uganda is that once you equip PVATs with teaching strategies, lesson plan development and implementation, classroom management, and student assessment you are likely to produce effective teachers. However, this general belief is debatable.

During teacher preparation, PVATs are taught the skills of planning to teach through designing lesson plans, lesson objectives, lesson activities, teaching aids, lesson presentation and classroom management (DSE, 2002). Knowledge of planning to teach also refers to curriculum, syllabi and school timetables (Musingafi et al, 2015). When PVATs acquire knowledge of planning to teach, it means that they are in a position to structure different lessons that suit different learning environment, age level, and method of delivery that is affordable at that moment and space (Ssegantebuka, 2018).

Other skills methods course avails to PVATs during teacher preparation, is the knowledge of learners. The knowledge of learners in this research refers to knowledge of learners' developmental stages which include; social growth, perceptual growth, intellectual growth, emotional growth, creative, and aesthetic (Lowenfeld & Brittain, 1987). It is of great importance for PVATs to acquire knowledge of learners' developmental stages in visual arts for it aids in selecting and sequencing experiences for quality learning, teaching strategies and other resources necessary in teaching, since knowledge of cognitive and emotional development influences the acquisition of skills in all aspects of art education (NAEA, 1999).

Through teaching methods, teachers facilitate the learning of particular content. Therefore, during methods course, PVATs learn several teaching strategies or teaching methods some of which are referred to as teacher-centred and others are learner-centred. Although PVATs learn about teacher-centred teaching methods, they are discouraged on using them often; they are encouraged to use learner-centred teaching methods. The most preferred teaching methods in VA include; workshops, seminar, project, group work, demonstration, observation, exhibition and critiquing (Ssegantebuka, 2017). Several researchers support the use of the above-mentioned teaching methods which stress inquiry, self-expression, Socratic teaching, individual coaching, student participation in their learning, and personalized instruction. For they reinforce better development of the higher mental processes and skills (Clark & Starr, 1986).

The methods course is also known for introducing PVATs to the teaching and learning process among others. Assessment can be defined as the systematic collection, review and use of information about educational programs to improve student learning (Swearingen, 2002). In most cases assessment focuses on; what students know and can do, and what values they have when they graduate. Assessment is an ongoing process of setting high expectations for student learning. It measures progress toward established learning outcomes, provides a basis for reflection, discussion and gives feedback to improve school academic programs (Israel, 2005). However, in (visual) art education, assessment is mainly subjective rather than being objective, but, tutors are expected to develop expertise in the assessment as part of their professional preparation (Ssegantebuka, 2017). Assessments in visual arts include actual performances in the forms of created artworks, essays and critical responses, interpretations and evaluations of works of art. Methods course still considers multiple methods of assessment, formal and informal, formative and summative, and a range of assessment strategies such as portfolios, journals, class critiques and discussions as crucial (Ssegantebuka, 2018). Therefore, it was in the interest of the researcher to find out PVATs' perceptions of the effectiveness of their methods course in NTCs in Uganda. The reviewed literature so far indicates the central importance of the methods course in the preparation of PVATs in NTCs in Uganda. Thus, the research objectives for this research are:

- a) Investigating the effectiveness of the methods course in equipping pre-service teachers with the knowledge and skills of teaching during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda
- b) Finding out how often tutors conduct the methods course during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda
- c) Examining the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of teaching and learning resources during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda
- d) Finding out the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of lesson planning and implementation during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda
- e) Investigating the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of teaching methods during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda
- f) Examining the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of assessment strategies during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

4. Methodology of Research

4.1 Research Design

The research followed a quantitative, descriptive research design. The research aimed at investigating the second year PVATs' perception of the effectiveness of their methods

course in equipping them with the knowledge and skills of teaching during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda and how it improves their teaching competence level.

4.2 Participants

The second-year diploma in secondary education (DSE) PVATs, constituted the targeted population for this research. These PVATs were those admitted on a visual arts education program in one of the NTCs in Uganda. These PVATs had just returned from six weeks of school practice done in several secondary schools as chosen by an individual trainee. The researcher worked with 52 PVATs, of whom 29(56%) male and 23(44%) female who willingly signed consent forms and completed and returned the questionnaires that were distributed.

4.3 Data Collection

PVATs who participated in this research were subjected to a self-constructed questionnaire. The items of the questionnaire focused on PVATs' gender; their general view about methods course; conducting of methods course; teaching and learning resources; lesson planning and implementation; knowledge of a variety of teaching methods and PVATs' use of assessment strategies.

4.4 Data Analysis

The data collected through the questionnaires were analysed using the descriptive statistics and then was presented in table format.

5. Results

5.1 Gender

Out of the 52 PVATs who participated in the research, 29 (56%) were male, while 23 (44%) were female.

5.2 Investigating the effectiveness of the methods course in equipping pre-service teachers with the knowledge and skills of teaching during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

This objective sought to find out the effectiveness of the methods course in equipping pre-service teachers with the knowledge and skills of teaching. The results are shown in Table 1.

PVATs 40(77%) indicated that they had offered the methods course during their pre-service teacher preparation. While 20(38%) agreed that their tutors handled the methods course content adequately, 32(62%) opposed to the way tutors handled the methods course content. About the way tutors conducted class projects/assignments for methods course, 17(33%) were in agreement with the tutors. However, the biggest number of PVATs 35(67%) disagreed with the way tutors conducted class projects/assignment. To them, it was not satisfying. In the same way, 23(44%) indicated

that their tutors explicitly explained to them the concept of art education (*methods course*). But 29(56%) who are the majority disagreed with the way tutors explained to them the concept of art education (*methods course*).

Table 1: General views about methods course

	Yes	No	Total
Have you offered a methods course during your pre-service teacher preparation?	40 (77%)	12 (23%)	52
Has the methods course content been adequately handled by the Tutors?	20 (38%)	32 (62%)	52
Has your tutor adequately conducted class assignments for the methods course?	17 (33%)	35 (67%)	52
Has your tutor explicitly explained to you the concept of art education?	23 (44%)	29 (56%)	52

Results in Table 1 show that majority of the PVATs who participated in this research had offered the methods course. However, they unanimously disagreed with the way tutors handled the methods course content, class projects/assignment and the way they explained to them the concept of art education (*methods course*), which calls for urgent attention.

5.3 Finding out how often tutors conduct the methods course during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

This objective sought to find out how often tutors conduct the methods course during teacher preparation. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: How tutors conduct methods course

Conducting methods course	Often	Rarely	Total
How often have you had lectures for the methods course?	14 (27%)	38 (73%)	52
How often did you write notes for the methods course?	10 (19%)	42 (81%)	52
How often did you conduct micro teaching as a way of putting theory into practice?	17 (33%)	35 (67%)	52
How often did you participate in assessing assignments given to you?	30 (58%)	22 (42%)	52

As indicated in Table 2, 38(%) stated that they rarely had methods course lectures. Similarly, a large number of PVATs 42(81%) rarely wrote notes for methods course during their teacher preparation at college. Considering how often tutors conducted micro teaching as a way of putting theory into practice 35(67%) PVATs indicated that they rarely had microteaching. This result is a cause for concern. On the contrary, 30(58%) indicated that they often participated in assessing assignments given to them as far as methods course was concerned. However, 22(42%) PVATs who stated that they rarely participated in assessing assignments in methods course cannot be ignored.

5.4 Examining the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of teaching and learning resources during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

This objective sought to find out the PVATs knowledge of a variety of teaching and learning resources during teacher preparation. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Teaching and learning resources

Methods course prepared me to:	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Not taught	Total
Design a good lesson plans	34 (65%)	18 (35%)	00 (00%)	52
Design a good scheme of work	39 (75%)	13 (25%)	00 (00%)	52
Use a well-designed record of work done	38 (73%)	14 (27%)	00 (00%)	52
Designing and using effective teaching aids	20 (38%)	32 (62%)	00 (00%)	52
Prepare and use improvised art-materials, and tools	16 (31%)	36 (69%)	00 (00%)	52
Use available art materials, tools and equipment	36 (69%)	16 (31%)	00 (00%)	52
Use audio-visual resources in my lessons	11 (21%)	14 (27%)	27 (52%)	52
Use computer(s) as a tool in art lessons	07 (14%)	11 (21%)	34 (65%)	52
Use art textbooks for information search	15 (29%)	28 (54%)	09 (17%)	52

As Table 3 shows that, 34(65%) PVATs could design a good lesson plan. 39(75%) were able to design a good scheme of work. 38(73%) could design a good record of work. 36(69%) PVATs were prepared to use available art materials, tools and equipment. However, 32(62%) were not satisfied with designing and using effective teaching aids. About improvised art-materials and tools, 36(69%) PVATs were dissatisfied with preparing and using improvised art-materials, and tools. While 28(54%) were not satisfied with the way they were taught how to use art textbooks for information search. Majority of the PVATs 27(52%) indicated that use of audio-visual resources was not taught to them at all and 34(65%) stated that they were not taught at all how to use the computer as a tool in art lessons. The results in Table 3 indicated that a considerable number of PVATs were still lacking knowledge of a variety of teaching and learning resources in pertinent areas. For example; 18(35%) PVATs were dissatisfied with designing a good lesson; 13(25%) were dissatisfied with designing a good scheme of work; 14(27%) were dissatisfied with designing a good record of work; 16(31%) were dissatisfied with available art-material, tools and equipment; 14(27%) were dissatisfied with using audiovisual resources and 11(21%) were dissatisfied with using computer as a tool in art lessons. These are also causes of concern as far as teaching and learning are concerned.

5.5 Finding out the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of lesson planning and implementation during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

This objective sought to find out the PVATs knowledge of lesson planning and implementation during teacher preparation. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Lesson planning and implementation

Methods course prepared me to:	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Total
Introduce my lessons effectively during teaching.	34 (65%)	18 (35%)	52
Effectively present my lessons during teaching.	37 (71%)	15 (29%)	52
Evaluate my lessons during teaching.	20 (38%)	32 (62%)	52
Summarise and conclude my lessons during teaching.	15 (29%)	37 (71%)	52
Manage my classroom for effective teaching and learning.	25 (48%)	27 (52%)	52
Give relevant assessment and feedback to my students	19 (37%)	33 (63%)	52
Develop time management skills.	37 (71%)	15 (29%)	52
Write clear and achievable lesson objectives	19 (37%)	33 (63%)	52
Encourage students' participation and interaction in the lesson.	38 (73%)	14 (27%)	52

In Table 4, 34(65%) PVATs reported that the methods course satisfactorily prepared them to effectively introduce the lessons during teaching; 37(71%) were able to effectively present their lessons during teaching; 37(71%) developed time management skills and 38(73%) were satisfied with the way they could encourage students to participate and interact in the lesson. Of concern in this research, were PVATs, who expressed their dissatisfaction in evaluating their lessons 32(62%); summarise and conclude their lessons 37(71%); effective classroom management 27(52%); give relevant feedback 33(63%) and writing clear and achievable lesson objectives was also at 33(63%). The findings indicated that there are areas of study tutors pay attention to and areas that are not well attended to. This means that a considerable number of PVATs were still struggling with the category of lesson planning and implementation.

5.6 Investigating the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of teaching methods during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

The following objective sought to establish if the PVATs knowledge of a variety of teaching methods during teacher preparation. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 shows 35(67%) were satisfied with their preparations to use demonstration method. In the same way, 31(60%) expressed their satisfaction with preparation to use teacher/student discussion methods, while 37(71%) PVATs indicated that methods course prepared them to use talk and chalk methods. Majority of the PVATs were satisfied with the use of group/work/discussion methods and 33(63%) indicated that methods course prepared them to use question and answer methods. However, a large number of PVATs 29(56%) expressed their dissatisfaction about their knowledge of lecture method as a teaching method; 27(52%) were dissatisfied with their knowledge of

project method, and 34(65%) were also dissatisfaction with their ability to use research method.

Table 5: Knowledge of a variety of teaching methods

Methods course has:	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Not taught	Total
Prepared me to use demonstration method	35 (67%)	17 (33%)	00 (00%)	52
Introduced me to lecture methods	12 (23%)	29 (56%)	11 (21%)	52
Introduced me to projects method	18 (35%)	27 (52%)	07 (13%)	52
Prepared me well to use teacher/student discussion	31 (60%)	13 (25%)	08 (15%)	52
Prepared me to use a research method	18 (35%)	34 (65%)	00 (00%)	52
Prepared me to use talk and chalk method	37 (71%)	15 (29%)	00 (00%)	52
Prepared me to use question and answers method	33 (63%)	19 (37%)	00 (00%)	52
Prepared me to use group/work/discussion method	39 (75%)	13 (25%)	00 (00%)	52

Although the results in Table 5 show that majority of the PVATs developed satisfactory knowledge of a variety of teaching methods, they are still problematic to a considerable number of PVATs. This means that tutors are mainly exposing PVATs to traditional teaching methods with little exposure to modern and learner-centred teaching methods.

5.7 Examining the extent to which methods course equips pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of assessment strategies during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda

The following objective sought to establish pre-service teachers with the knowledge of a variety of assessment strategies during teacher preparation. The results are shown in Table 6:

Table 6: Pre-service visual arts teachers' use of assessment strategies

Methods course has:	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Not taught	Total
Prepared me well to use exhibition strategies	15 (29%)	37 (71%)	00 (00%)	52
Equipped me with the skills to use critiques	10 (19%)	39 (75%)	03 (06%)	52
Prepared me to use practical tests	35 (67%)	14 (27%)	03 (06%)	52
Introduced me to individual/group presentations	40 (77%)	07 (13%)	05 (10%)	52
Prepared me to use portfolio	13 (25%)	07 (13%)	32 (62%)	52
Equipped me with the skills to use essays	11 (21%)	15 (29%)	26 (50%)	52
Equipped me with the skills to use multiple-choice questions	19 (37%)	12 (23%)	21 (40%)	52

The Table 6 shows that 35(67%) PVATs were satisfied with their preparations to use practice tests and 40(77%) were also satisfied with their ability to use individual/group

presentation assessment strategies. However, 37(71%) expressed dissatisfaction with their preparation to use exhibition strategies and 39(75%) were dissatisfied with their failure to acquire skills in using critique as assessment strategies. About portfolio as an assessment strategy, 32(62%) PVATs indicated that they were not taught at all how to use portfolio; 26(50%) were not taught at all how to use essays as assessment strategy in visual arts and 21(40%) also indicated that they were not taught at all how to use multiple choice questions as assessment strategies in visual arts during their methods course.

6. Discussion

This research aimed at investigating the second year PVATs' perceptions of the effectiveness of their methods course in equipping them with the knowledge and skills of teaching during teacher preparation in NTCs in Uganda and how it improves their teaching competence levels. During pre-service teacher preparations, tutors are supposed to equip PVATs with the methods course content which include but not limited to learners' developmental stages, teaching and learning resources, lesson planning and implementation, knowledge of a variety of teaching methods and assessment strategies among others. On this note, the findings of the research show that the six weeks supervised school practice availed the majority of the PVATs the opportunity to assess the effectiveness of their methods course in equipping them with the knowledge and skills of teaching during the actual school practice. The PVATs responses indicated that their methods course was not all that effective in equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills they needed for school practice as seen in Table 1 and Table 2. They were not comfortable with the way tutors handled the methods course content and assignments. They rarely had lectures for methods course, rarely copied notes and they did not have enough practice of what they were supposed to teach during actual school practice. Such practices contradicted with Musingafi et al (2015) suggestion of equipping pre-service teachers with the knowledge of planning to teach.

The results in Table 3 indicated that majority of the PVATs were satisfied with their methods course in preparing them in designing and using teaching and learning resources before going for the actual school practice. However, a considerable number of PVATs also expressed their dissatisfaction with their methods course' failure to prepare them in designing and using effective teaching aids, preparing and using improvised art materials and tools, and using art textbooks for information search. The research further revealed that during methods course the majority of the PVATs were not exposed to the use of audio-visual resources, and computers as tools in art lessons. This is in line with Ssegantebuka, (2018) suggestion that exposing PVATs to the use of technology in teaching during the teacher preparation calls for urgent attention.

The findings of this research indicated that the majority of the PVATs were satisfactorily prepared in the category of lesson planning and implementation, as indicated in Table 4. Of concern, is the large number of PVATs who expressed their dissatisfaction in evaluating their lessons; summarise and conclude their lessons;

effective classroom management; give relevant feedback and writing clear and achievable lesson objectives. This is attributed to the fact that tutors pay attention to some areas and omit other areas as observed by Nbina (2012). This was due to limited knowledge tutors had in the methods course. This means that a considerable number of PVATs were still struggling with the category of lesson planning and implementation.

The results in Table 5 show that majority of the PVATs developed satisfactory knowledge a variety of teaching methods. Eison (2010) shows the need for a teacher to develop the ability to use several teaching materials. Simply because knowing a variety of teaching methods offers different learning opportunities in a learning situation. Although the majority of PVATs indicated that their methods course equipped them with the knowledge of a variety of teaching methods, these were mainly traditional and teacher-centred teaching methods. The findings further indicated a large number of PVATs who were dissatisfied with their knowledge of project methods and research methods. This means that tutors need to refocus methods course content to emphasise more of active and learner-centred teaching methods as suggested by Clark and Starr (1986), during the preparation of PVATs in NTCs in Uganda.

Although the majority of the PVATs indicated satisfactory preparation in the use of practice tests and the use of individual/group presentation, a big number of PVATs were unsatisfactorily prepared in the use of exhibition strategies and critique as assessment strategies. This is attributed to the fact that tutors commonly use practical test in art teaching and also use group presentations in microteaching practice. Of concern, are the three areas which were not taught at all to a considerable number of PVATs which included the use of portfolio, essays and multiple-choice questions, as shown in Table 6. Further findings indicate that several PVATs were still challenging to apply some of the assessment strategies including some of the assessment strategies they claimed to have satisfactorily learnt. In this case, therefore, there is a need to teach PVATs several assessment strategies and this should be done when they are still undergoing their training at college (Clark and Starr, 1986; NAEA, 1999; Ssegantebuka, 2018).

7. Conclusion

The overall findings showed that the methods course averagely equipped the PVATs with the knowledge and skills they needed for school practice. This is attributed to the fact that a considerably large number of PVATs expressed their dissatisfaction with their methods course's ability to effectively equip them with the knowledge and skills needed for school practice. For example, the majority of the PVATs offered the methods course, but most of them were not comfortable with the way tutors handled the methods course content and class assignments. Tutors rarely conducted lectures in methods course and did not give methods course notes to PVATs. Additionally, PVATs were also found with limited knowledge of using a variety of teaching and learning resources, knowledge of lesson planning and implementation, knowledge of a variety of teaching methods and

limited knowledge of using a variety of assessment strategies. All these were identified as issues of concern and the researcher called for urgent attention to them.

8. Recommendations

Methods course content is a vital component of the teacher education program. It offers pre-service teachers with the opportunity to acquire knowledge and skills for teaching as well as putting theory into practice while still at college. The practice is supposed to be done in preparation for school practice in secondary schools. Therefore, there is a need for NTCs' administration to revise the methods course content and include technology-based content. The methods course content should also be taught right from the first term of an academic year for the effective coverage of the needed content. There is a need to refresh tutors' knowledge of the methods course content. Once done it will reduce on the omission of content were tutors' have limited knowledge. NTCs' administration needs to improve on monitoring of the teaching and learning in the methods course to ensure regular attendance of both tutors and PVATs. Allocate more time to practicing the content learned in the methods course. Once done it will help PVATs acquire knowledge and skills of teaching in any given context, and before actual school practice.

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